

METHOD

- Observations on the 3rd and 5th day, samples health condition check
- Food (grouper fish, pig liver) were placed in the center
- Flatworms foraging behavior were recorded for 30 mins

Identifying the Foraging Behavior of Flatworms During Regeneration

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Abstract. Flatworms are famous for their regeneration ability or binomial diffusion. Because the feeding behavior of flatworms after regeneration remains uninvestigated, we conducted experiments on the foraging behavior of freshwater *Dugesia* flatworm specimens after regeneration. The flatworms were placed in petri dishes with freshwater after dissecting. On the 3rd and 5th days, food was placed in the petri dish, and then the behavior of flatworms was recorded for 30 minutes. The results of both our experiments show that dissected flatworms do not have foraging behavior, which was similar to a study on marine polyclad flatworm.

1. Introduction

Flatworms are mostly benthic. There are over 10000 species of flatworms worldwide, which can be classified into marine flatworms (Turbellaria) and freshwater flatworms (*Dugesia*)^[1-2]. Flatworms are bilaterally symmetrical and consist of a defined head and tail region; they also kept a central nervous system containing a brain and a nerve cord. Interestingly, these small aquatic creatures possess an amazing ability to regenerate themselves through the specialized pluripotent stem cells they produce.

Figure 1. The appearance and basic structures of a *Dugesia*.flatworm

Dugesia, a genus of the freshwater flatworm (Fig.1), was the target species of this study. This species appears to have an elongated body with a slightly triangle-shaped head. A previous study reported the regeneration of *Dugesia* flatworm species^[3] enduring mitosis activity. The report indicated the fact that a biphasic pattern was developed during the mitosis activity during regeneration, which basically illustrates the experiment on 2 identical flatworms were proceed during the process of regeneration where one flatworm was dissected into two pieces. The result of that study revealed that there are major differences in mitosis activity during regeneration between flatworms and classical regeneration models such as Annelida^[3]. The other study similarly reported the feeding behavior of dissected marine flatworms due to chemical stimulation and vibration^[4]. The result of that study indicates that the control (uncut) flatworms presented foraging behavior during their observation and responses to food. Furthermore, the study indicated that a flatworm's brain has a coordination function that

coordinates the basic motor neurons underlying specific patterns of muscular activity in the nervous system.

When a flatworm is dissected into two pieces, which can be identified as the head section and tail section, the regeneration of the tail is necessary for the head section. Correspondingly, the regeneration of the head is necessary for the tail section. Theoretically, the one that forages for food resources first will have the best chance of surviving. But, after being cut, which section, the head or tail section, could finish regeneration earlier and start eating first? Reports about freshwater flatworms' foraging behaviour during regeneration, however, are insufficient and undiscovered. In fact, the foraging behaviour of dissected flatworms is relatively important since in the wild, the flatworms might get attacked by other predators and detached into pieces. Therefore, the process of regeneration was required. Hence, it is necessary to assess the foraging behaviour of flatworms during regeneration.

In this study, we will investigate the foraging behavior of freshwater *Dugesia* flatworms after it was dissected and determine whether they will or will not have the action of foraging after the dissection.

2. Materials and methods.

2.1. Materials required

Ten petri dishes, pipets, six freshwater *Dugesia* flatworm, RenYue microscope (RY7045-B1), pig livers (0.94g), grouper fish (1.73g), distilled water, cutting knife, box container, black marker, recording device (iPad), OHAUS electronic balance (PX523ZH).

2.2. Experiment methods

Freshwater flatworm specimens were acquired from a lab aquarium with running freshwater in 2022, 14th of July, Shenzhen. Foraging behaviour during regeneration experiments was proceeded in the lab after it was acquired from the aquarium, ten plastic petri dishes with an inside diameter of 9 cm were applied as container of flatworms. Six freshwater flatworms were transferred into 6 dishes by pipetting from the freshwater aquarium. Then about 15 mL of fresh distilled water were added to the petri dish to ensure the living habitat of the flatworms. Two flatworms were kept in a petri dish, other 4 flatworms were transferred by pipetting in to new petri dishes and placed under microscope and then separated into 2 groups. Each replicate group contains 2 flatworms and were dissected with a sharp cutting knife either horizontally or vertically, as displayed in Fig. 2. The 4 dissected sections, which were the head and tail sections of two horizontal cut flatworms, and two left and right of two vertically cut flatworms, were transferred into 4 new petri dishes through pipetting. The uncut, Horiz.head, Horiz.tail, Verti.left, Verti.right flatworm sections/specimen were stored in a larger container and standed in obscure area for the night.

Figure 2. Dissection of *Dugesia* flatworm specimens

In total, 10 flatworm sections/specimens were kept in the 10 petri dishes with 15 mL of distilled water each. Flatworms were observed under a dissecting microscope every two days until the 5th day of observation under the course of regeneration.

The first foraging behavior experiment was conducted on the 3rd day of observation. The flatworms were firstly observed under the microscope to check the health condition of the flatworms (Fig. 3). The vertical right flatworm in replicate 1 was disintegrated and dissolved, but the others were all maintained in a healthy physical state. The food for flatworm, which was grouper fish meat, was taken out from the refrigerator and placed in distilled water to unfreeze. The grouper fish was placed on an electronic balance to measure its mass. Then, 1.73 grams of grouper fish was dissected with a knife and added to the mortar and pistol. 1 mL of distilled water was added to the mortar and pistol and the fish meat was homogenized.

Replicate 1 was used as the experimental groups. However, the flatworms were at the edge of the petri dishes, the grouper fish paste was placed in the middle of the Petri dishes. The recording device was placed above 5 petri dishes. Thirty minutes of recording flatworms foraging behaviour were performed.

Figure 3. Images of flatworms was taken on the during the 3rd day of regeneration.

Images of flatworms during regeneration was chosen randomly.

a. R1 Horiz. Tail; b. R1 Horiz. Head; c. R1 Verti. Right; d. R1 Verti. Left; e. R1 uncut; f. R2 uncut

The second foraging behavior experiment was conducted on the 5th day of the experiment. The flatworms were first observed under a dissecting microscope to check their health condition of the flatworms (Fig. 4). The uncut flatworm in replicate 2 was released and sent back to the freshwater aquarium, and 2 flatworms in Replicate 1 were dissolved, but others were all alive. The food for flatworm, pig liver, was taken out from the refrigerator and placed in distilled water to unfreeze. The pig liver was placed on an electronic balance to measure its mass. Then, 0.94 grams of pig liver was dissected with a knife and added to the triturating dish, 1 mL of distilled water was also added to the triturating dish, and triturated until a paste. Replicate 2 was used as the experimental groups. However, the flatworms were at the edge of the Petri dishes, the pig liver paste was placed in the middle of the petri dishes. The recording device was placed above 4 Petri dishes. Similarly, thirty minutes of recording flatworms' foraging behavior are required.

Figure 4. Images of flatworms was taken on the during the 5th day of regeneration. **a.** R2 Horiz. Tail (around 2.5mm long); **b.** R2 Verti. Right (around 3mm long); **c.** R2 Horiz. Head (around 2.5mm long); **d.** R2 Verti. Left (around 2mm long). Images of flatworms during regeneration was chosen randomly; and the distances between grids are 1mm.

3. Results

3.1. Regeneration of dissected flatworms

The conditions of the flatworm were observed under a microscope on the 3rd day after the dissection. On the 3rd day, all the dissected flatworm remained in a lively state, no significant regeneration of flatworms was detected. The head section of the flatworm was still without a tail region, and did not show any regeneration (Fig. 3b). On the other hand, one of the flatworms was dissolved in the water under an unknown factor. The second observation was on the 5th day after dissection, a new tail region was visible in the head section of the dissected flatworm. However, the regenerated tail regions appeared to be incomplete, and the posterior end was unpigmented (Fig. 4c). The health condition of flatworms in the 3rd and 5th day was accessed and summarized in Table. 1.

flatworms	Health state 2022/7/13	2022/7/15	2022/7/17	Foraging behavior
R1 uncut	Alive	N.A		
R1 Horiz. Head	Alive	Alive	Alive	N.A
R1 Horiz. Tail	Alive	Alive	Alive	N.A
R1 Vertical left	Alive	Alive	Alive	N.A
R1 Vertical right	Alive	Alive	Alive	N.A
R2 uncut	alive	Alive	Alive	Yes
R2 Horiz. Head	alive	Alive	N.A	No
R2 Horiz. Tail	alive	Alive	Alive	No
R2 Vertical left	alive	Alive	N.A	No
R2 vertical right	N.A	N.A		

Table 1. Table of each flatworm's health condition, and its foraging behaviour.

3.2. Feeding experiments results

During the 3rd day of the experiment, all three dissected flatworms in replicate 1 (vertical left, horizontal head horizontal tail) presented no reaction towards their food during the 30 minutes of recording. However, the control group, the uncut flatworm ate the grouper fish at 11 minutes 20 seconds during recording. (Fig. 5, Fig. 6)

Figure 5. Observation at the beginning of experiment on the 3rd day, showing the initial position flatworm. **a.** R2 Horiz. Tail (around 2.5mm long); **b.** R2 Vert. Right (around 3mm long); **c.** R2 Horiz. Head (around 2.5mm long); **d.** R2 Vert. Left (around 2mm long).

Figure 6. Observation during the experiment in the 3rd day

which shows the positions of flatworms at 11 minutes 26 seconds after the recording start. **a.** R2 Horiz. Tail (around 2.5mm long); **b.** R2 Vert. Right (around 3mm long); **c.** R2 Horiz. Head (around 2.5mm long); **d.** R2 Vert. Left (around 2mm long).

Similarly, during the 5th day of the experiment, the four cuts of flatworms in Replicate 2 (vertical left, vertical right, horizontal head, horizontal head) displayed no reaction towards the given food throughout the 30 minutes recording.

To conclude, according to our experimental results on the 3rd and 5th day during regeneration, all flatworms that were dissected displayed an uninterested behavior in foraging for food; contrastingly, the one that was not dissected did forage for food during the experiment (Fig. 7, Fig. 8), which was similar to a previous work done ^[5].

Figure 7. Observation at the beginning of experiment on the 5th day, which shows the initial position flatworm.

Figure 8. Observation at the end of experiment in the 5th day, which shows the positions of flatworms at 30minutes after the recording start.

4. Discussion

According to the results from our experiment, freshwater *Dugesia* flatworms have no foraging behavior on the 5th day of regeneration after being dissected. Our hypothesis is that the flatworms do not have foraging behavior during regeneration because the flatworms without a head cannot sense the chemical from the food and control their body to move toward the food because the nerve system cannot work, and the flatworm without a tail cannot eat the food because of lacking ingestion organs.

A previous study investigated marine polyclad flatworm species' foraging behavior in response to odorant chemical stimulus [2,5]. The paper reported that under chemical stimulations, only the control group flatworm and healed flatworms during mitosis activity forages for food. Our results are consistent with those in which our control group also foraged for food on the 3rd of the experiment. Our experimental results on the freshwater *Dugesia* flatworms, therefore, are significant to future studies on the natural behavior of freshwater flatworm experiments.

Our experiments have several limitations. Firstly, one of the flatworms from both replicates was dissolved on the 3rd day of the experiment, therefore, we lack one sample in each replicate, and therefore we just analyzed the remaining samples in replicates to form a complete set of data. Secondly, we lost the fed specimen in the second replication, so our data might not be comparable to replicate 1. Thirdly, the food sources were different between the two experiments, and there may be differences in food preferences. Nevertheless, our experiment contributed toward understanding the proper foraging behavior of flatworms after dissection during regeneration, although there are numerous shortages and immeasurable factors in our experiment.

Future studies can apply different flatworm species such as marine species, to conduct the foraging behavior of regenerating flatworms in various species. Also, more work can focus on observing the foraging behavior of flatworms for a longer time. In addition, a more diverse experimental environment such as striking the flatworms with different light sources and applying different chemical stimulations might be considered as well.

To conclude, we found that the flatworm does not have foraging behavior after dissection until it heals, this brought contribution and knowledge to the study of dissection flatworms.

References:

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